

The Effects of a Brief Game-Based Mobile Phone Detox on Executive Functioning among Undergraduate Students: An Experimental Study Using Ludo

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Abstract

Overuse of the smartphone has been increasingly related to attentional fragmentation and impaired executive functioning, especially in young adults. Although the available studies indicate that restricted access to smartphones can positively affect executive functioning, limited research has examined whether structured offline activities during mobile phone detox can improve executive functioning. The current research was an experimental investigation into whether an experimental, game-based mobile phone detox intervention would have immediate effects of enhancing executive functioning in undergraduate students. It used a randomized pretest-posttest parallel-group experimental design, with 60 undergraduate students selected through purposive sampling and equally divided into a Ludo-based mobile phone detox group and a control group. The intervention involved voluntary abstinence from smartphone use while participants engaged in the board game Ludo, whereas the control group kept their phones and continued with their usual behavior. The dependent variables were attention and working memory, which were measured with the help of N-back task and Digit Span task. The Smartphone Addiction Scale-Short Version was used to measure the pretreatment levels of problematic smartphone use. Findings were partially in favor of the main hypothesis. The mobile detox group was much better at the Shapes N-back task at post-test with a very large effect size ($d = 1.58$) and showed a significant advantage on overall Digit Span scores ($p = .021$, $d = .61$). Digit Span within-group gains were also found in both groups, indicating the occurrence of practice effects. The results of the study show that a short-term, structured mobile phone detox results in task-specific improvements in executive functioning, especially in visuospatial attention and general working memory capacity.

INTRODUCTION

Mobile phones are now an integral part of our life especially to the younger generations who consider it normal to have constant access (Dan & Zamfirescu, 2022), and it is also socially approved. Although these gadgets have undisputed advantages in the access of information, communication (Calderón-Garrido et al., 2022) and entertainment, there is a growing concern regarding the effects on cognitive functioning wherein excessive and uncontrollable use of these gadgets is causing problems (Oyasor, 2025). According to massive reports, smartphones have become the most common medium for how individuals interact with digital content, and social media represent a significant part of their everyday activity (Kemp, 2023). Notably, the percentage of individuals reporting being dissatisfied with the nature of their mobile phone usage is rather high, which is why it is possible to assume at the very least that there is an increasing number of individuals becoming aware of the possibility of habitual mobile phone use being inconsistent with their personal objectives, professional activities, and health (Olson et al., 2022).

In addition to subjective issues, objective studies have reported objective cognitive effects of heavy smartphone use. The research shows that passive phone-related considerations, including notifications or the physical location of the gadget, can disrupt attentional resources and negatively affect the working memory and task performance (Stothart et al., 2015; Ward et al., 2017). These results are especially applicable to academic situations, where the problem of sustained attention and executive control are the keys to learning and performance. More pervasive dysfunctional effects of longer-term and impulsive use of devices have also been associated with the loss of academic interest and the quality of social interactions (Amiri et al., 2020).

Smartphone Use and Cognitive Interference

The adoption of smartphones in everyday activities has been followed by increased anxiety towards how people are affected by them in terms of higher-order thinking. The evidence based on empirical studies is more and more inclined to the direction that smartphone-related distractions work not only during active usage but also when the device is not used and forms a sort of cognitive interference that impairs task-orientated performances (Ward et al., 2017). In experimental studies, such access or exposure to a smartphone alone was found to have a negative impact on the working memory capacity, attentional control, and fluid intelligence, especially when faced with a cognitively demanding task (Parry, 2024; Skowronek et al., 2023).

It is believed that this interference results due to smartphones being salient cues that are related to habitual checking behaviours. When people are trying to repress these urges, the existence of cognitive resources is focused on self-control instead of the performance of tasks (Fabio et al., 2022). Consequently, performance declines are observed even in the cases when people themselves avoid contact with their devices. These results refute the idea that distraction is entirely a matter of screen time and instead point to the cognitive price attached to the availability of constant devices (Canale et al., 2019).

Executive Functioning: Working Memory and Attention

Executive functioning is a group of higher-order cognitive functions that allow people to regulate attention, retain and manipulate information and adapt behavior to the specifications of a task. Attentional control, working memory, and inhibitory control are core elements of executive functioning that are necessary in academic learning and goal-oriented behavior (Friedman & Robbins,

2022). Of these elements, the working memory is the major constituent of executive functioning since it entails both short-term storage and manipulation of information in the process of complex thinking. The most notable theories of working memory view it as a system that is closely connected with the attentional control and executive regulation (Baddeley, 2000; Draheim et al., 2022). Therefore, the examination of executive functioning in experimental studies is often conducted through the working memory tasks (Naveh-Benjamin & Cowan, 2023).

Activities like the N-back paradigm and the Digit Span test involve the ability of an individual to retain, update, and manipulate information as well as keep track of information occurring in the environment, which are activities that involve direct involvement of the executive control mechanisms (Gajewski et al., 2018; Idowu et al., 2024). The N-back tasks have been under various modifications and improvements; it has also been validated among Pakistani population (Mujitaba et al., 2025). Hence, working memory capacity and attentional control measures such as the Digit Span and N-back tasks are good predictors of the performance of executive functioning.

The laboratory-related studies show that the working memory tasks (digit span and visual memory paradigm) are worse when smartphones are present, or when it is believed to be available, indicating that executive capacity is impaired in conditions of competing attentional salience (Oyasar, 2025; Ward et al., 2017). Such effects are particularly intense when complex or effortful cognitive processes are involved, which further supports the concept that the executive functioning is sensitive to environmental distractions consuming limited cognitive resources.

Mobile Phone Detox and Offline Engagement

The idea of mobile phone detox has been in focus as a possible remedy to attentional overload due to the smartphone-related cognitive interference (Castelo et al., 2025). Mobile phone detox typically entails a scheduled withdrawal of phone usage, and in that context, one can focus their cognitive processes on other things, rather than a smartphone.

Offline activities involving long-term focused attention, rule-based action, and interpersonal communication like board games (Zulkefli & Mohd Juned, 2023), might be one of the exceptionally useful intervention methods against smartphone-based cognitive depletion. These activities have the potential to decrease extraneous cognitive load by eliminating access to mobile devices and involving participants in goal-focused and organized tasks, and allowing redirection of executive resources to processing the task in question (Vita-Barrull et al., 2023). Nevertheless, there is still little empirical evidence assessing the short time real effect of such interventions on attention, and working memory especially in undergraduate populations.

Theoretical Framework: Cognitive Load Theory and Executive Functioning

The current research is based on the Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) which provides a lens to interpret the idea of smartphone usage and its impact on executive functioning. CLT suggests that the working memory is limited in capacity, implying that cognitive performance is determined by the efficiency with which mental resources are allocated. The theory uses three types of loads, intrinsic load (complexity in tasks), extraneous load (distractions that are irrelevant), and germane load (finding meaning and processing) (Sweller, 1988, 2011).

Smartphones are placed as a great burden of load. Their very existence, even in the face of

idle time, causes the attentional resources to be diverted off the task in hand and the executive functions such as the ability to focus on a specific task, working memory and impulse control are left with less mental capacity (Oyasar, 2025). The detox of mobile phones interventions can be seen, then, as an attempt to decrease this extraneous burden. CLT is however of the opinion that it is not enough to eliminate a distraction but rather the liberated cognitive resources must be diverted to meaningful activity so that any meaningful good is obtained. At this point, germane load comes in.

In this case, offline board games are a good behavioral alternative. They require long term attention, following rules and constant updating of the mind all of which involve executive functioning (Zulkefli & Mohd Juned, 2023). The confounding of the elimination of access to smartphones and the introduction of an organized offline task is hypothesized to reduce extraneous load and simultaneously stimulate the occurrence of germane load, which creates an environment conducive to attention and working memory improvements.

Literature Review

The increasing body of experimental studies has outgrown the correlational results to explore the question of whether the lack of access to smartphones, which is often called digital detox, has any quantifiable impact on psychological well-being and cognitive functioning. Smartphones are believed to impose ongoing stresses on the limited cognitive reserves not only when actively used but also the cognitive effort to avoid the temptation of checking the phone even when not in use (Oyasar, 2025; Ward et al., 2017). Interventions based on detox thus should help to decrease this long-term cognitive load, by limiting mobile internet access or eliminating smartphones in the environment.

Experiments in the laboratory have given preliminary results that even a small exposure to a smartphone can affect cognitive ability negatively. The working memory capacity and sustained attention are also found to be impaired when having a smartphone in the room, even when it is turned off (Niu et al., 2022; Ward et al., 2017). Such results are in line with the brain drain hypothesis that suggests that smartphones drain attention resources because they are in the environment and are consumed by being salient, thereby reducing cognitive capacity to perform goal-oriented activities (Ward et al., 2017). Despite the fact that these effects are modest, as the meta-analyses indicate, they are statistically consistent across all studies, which means that smartphone presence is accompanied by a credible cognitive cost (Böttger et al., 2023; Parry, 2024). Field research has also demonstrated that a decrease in notifications and the blocking of mobile internet access can enhance the results of attentional control, well-being, and mental health, even within comparatively brief intervals (Brailovskaia et al., 2023; Castelo et al., 2025; Fitz et al., 2019).

Detox effects are not, however, consistently experienced. Personal traits, including impulsivity, excessive use of the smartphone, and fear of missing out (FoMO) mediate the level of cognitive interference when a phone is present (Canale et al., 2019; Niu et al., 2022). More emotionally impulsive people or more attached to their smartphone seem more susceptible to cognitive disruption, whereas people with better self-regulatory skills are less likely to face any cognitive cost in general (Fabio et al., 2022).

Offline Behavioral Substitution and Board Games as a Mobile Phone Detox Strategy
There is an emerging literature that points to the shortcomings of detox methods that are based on passive abstinence. There is some evidence indicating that restriction combined with organized offline experiences can

generate more cognitive and well-being effects than restriction (Farrukh et al., 2025). Lack of an effective alternative means that the non-use of smartphones can lead to boredom and attentional drift, reducing the efficacy of compliance and detox (Muench & Muench, 2020).

Board games are one of the most promising but underdeveloped substitution strategies. They need long-term attention, adherence to rules, planning, and inhibition of response, as well as constant observation of the evolving game positions, which involve the core executive functions (Herrero et al., 2025). Research on education has shown that guided game-based tasks may reinforce working memory and cognitive functioning in situations where active rules are to be applied (Vita-Barrull et al., 2023). In a Cognitive Load Theory perspective, board games are simultaneously decreasing extraneous load by replacing digital distractions and increasing germane load by playing a goal-oriented game. Although this fits into the theory, board games are still under-researched as a formal detox method, with the majority of the existing literature on the topic being confined to digital restriction (Buskens, 2024). The present research aims at filling this gap by experimentally investigating the hypothesis of whether a short-term smartphone detox and participation in a board game can bring about short-term effects of attention and working memory among undergraduate students.

Rationale for the Present Study

Since the executive functioning has been shown to be susceptible to smartphone-related interference, and the theoretical potential of such a device disengagement-based intervention to achieve immediate changes in attention and working memory is significant, the current study aims to conduct an experimental study on whether a short mobile phone detox intervention can lead to immediate changes in attention and working

memory. This study will integrate the existing literature on the topic of digital distraction and executive control by utilizing an offline board game as the intervention and objective cognitive tasks as outcome measures.

Besides, increased evidence suggests that the availability of smartphones has the potential to disrupt executive functioning, and little experimental evidence exists to determine whether short, manipulated mobile phone detox interventions can have immediate cognitive effects. In addition, the published literature on detox has mainly centered on passive restriction or well-being, and little has been done regarding objective measures of executive functioning. The current study aimed at filling these gaps through experimental research of the short-term outcomes of a mobile phone detox intervention that was conducted using an offline board game with undergraduate students. Based on the Cognitive Load Theory, the research question of interest was to ascertain whether temporary separation with smartphones with the inclusion of cognitively stimulating offline task would result in selective attention and working memory enhancement.

Methods

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess pretest to posttest changes in attention and working memory among participants receiving the mobile phone detox intervention.
2. To compare the effects of a short, guided mobile phone detox intervention, operationalized through playing an offline Ludo game, and a control condition on attention and working memory in undergraduate students.

Hypotheses

- Participants in the mobile phone detox group will show a significant improvement in attention and working memory from pretest to posttest following the intervention.

- The mobile detox group will show significantly greater improvement in attention and working memory compared to the control group following the intervention.

Research Design

The current research used a randomized pretest-posttest parallel-group experimental design with purposive sampling to determine the causal impact of a short-term mobile phone detox intervention on executive functioning in undergraduate students (Campbell & Stanley, 2015).

Sample

The study population consisted of university students who met the criteria for mobile phone addiction (SAS-SV cut-off score: ≥ 31 for male and ≥ 33 for females) as shown in Figure 1. Participants were recruited through purposive sampling based on SAS-SV cutoff scores (≥ 31 for males, ≥ 33 for females). From 224 screened students, 60 eligible participants were then randomly assigned to either the Mobile Detox Group or Control Group using the fish-bowl method. The respondents were between 18 and 25 years. There were 18 males and 12 females in each group. The sample size was deemed adequate for experimental research, as a statistical power level of 0.80 is generally recommended for detecting meaningful effects in behavioral studies (Cohen, 2013). The selected participants were randomly allocated into mobile detox and control group with equal probability. Both groups were provided with the same baseline measurements of the working memory and attentional control before and after the intervention period.

Figure 1

Selection of Sample and Assignment of Experimental Task

Note. SAS-SV = Smartphone Addiction Scale – Short Version (Kwon et al., 2013). Cutoff scores: Men ≥ 31 ; Women ≥ 33 . Both groups completed identical N-Back (Alphabets & Shapes) and Digit Span (forward, Backward) tasks at pretest and posttest. Board Ludo intervention applied: 2 games \times 20 min = 40 min, without mobile phones present.

Instruments and Measures

Smartphone Addiction Diagnostic

Problematic smartphone use along with sample screening for the study were accomplished through the Smartphone Addiction Scale-Short Version (SAS-SV) created by Kwon et al. (2013). It comprises 10-items and it is a self-report scale based on the original Smartphone Addiction Scale, resulting from the expert assessment of the items in a content validity

index process (Kwon et al., 2013). The answers were reported on a 6-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree) and higher scores (cut-off score of 31 in male and 33 in female) indicate more problematic smartphone use. The scale has shown excellent psychometrics such as high reliability ($\alpha = 0.91$) internal consistency and reasonable concurrent validity in the validation samples (Kwon et al., 2013). The SAS-SV was only used for screening the sample in the current study to make sure that the respondents are at the inclusion criteria of relatively high smartphone use.

N-Back Working Memory Task

The working memory performance was tested by the N-back task. The N-back tasks are highly suggested in testing the working memory as it involves individuals to retain, keep track and refresh the information on the fly (Baddeley et al., 1984). In the current experiment, the task was modified according to the approach presented by Mujitaba et al. (2024) and presented with the help of PsychoPy (version 24.04).

The experiment involved alphabet and shape trials which aimed at testing the capacity of the participants to keep updating and comparing incoming stimuli to the previously presented items. The trials started with a fixation cross of 0.5 seconds and then a stimulus appeared on the screen. In the alphabet trials, letters were presented randomly, and the participants had to respond to the question whether the letter that was cued at the moment had been present in the sequence 3 positions ago. Respondents were asked to press Y (yes) and N (no) as the answer.

After the alphabet trials, the participants did a try of shape trials, where colored shapes were used in place of letters. The participants in both conditions did 10 alphabets and 10 shapes trials and it was automatically recorded with the use of PsychoPy program. Right judgments were coded as correct judgments and wrong

judgments were recorded as errors. The given task design made it possible to evaluate the updating and attentional monitoring skills of participants in working memory (Mujitaba et al., 2024).

Figure 2

Schematic Presentation of Working Memory N-Back Task Trials: Alphabet and Shapes

Note. The provided figure depicts how the shape and alphabet trials were set in each session. The shape trials are presented on the right and alphabet trials are presented on the left. There is a fixation cross and an alphabet in a random sequence on the computer screen. The participant is required to make a judgment on whether the specific cued alphabet appeared three steps away following receiving a cue (an alphabet having a dot) by responding to the query with a yes response (Y) and no response (N). The shape trials used a similar setting with a range of shapes of orange color. Adapted from Mujitaba et al. (2024) and Mujitaba et al. (2025).

Digit Span Task (Attention and Concentration)

Attention and working memory capacity were measured with the help of the Digit Span task in the form of forward and backward recall conditions. It is an efficient and popular test of short-term memory and attention abilities where the participants repeat the number sequences in both forward and backward sequence (Grégoire & Van Der Linden, 1997;

Woods et al., 2011). Analysis was done using the standardized total span scores. The tasks were given one at a time in a low-distraction testing setting with individual cubicles and time-sensitive portions were timed with a stopwatch to provide consistency in administration.

Mobile Detox Group

The intervention involved the offline Ludo-playing session that lasted one session and was meant to serve as a mobile phone detox. The members of the mobile detox group were requested to voluntarily give up their mobile phones and engaged in ludo-based play time as part of the intervention. The game rules were given a short five minutes overview to make sure there was a similar understanding. The subjects then played two games of Ludo using a real board totaling 40 minutes. The game of Ludo was played by two individuals and all the sessions were overseen by the researcher.

Control Group

In the meantime, the control group participants retained their mobile phones and remained seated without any structured activity, reflecting their typical smartphone use behavior.

Procedure

The research was carried out in an organized fashion. Prior to data collection, the project received ethical approval from the Departmental Ethics Review Committee of GIFT University. The study adhered to the ethical guidelines for human subject research. The study's purpose, voluntary involvement, and the freedom to discontinue participation at any moment without consequence were explained to the participants. Prior to the study's commencement, all participants provided their informed consent.

Participants were recruited by class announcements in the university and then the selected participants finished the Smartphone

Addiction Scale-

Short Version (SAS-SV) as part of the screening process, followed by eligibility verification and informed consent. Eligible participants then completed baseline (pretest) assessments, which included the N-back task (letters and shapes variants) and the Digit Span task (forward and backward). A brief seated rest period followed the baseline assessment.

Next, participants assigned to the mobile phone detox group surrendered their phones, received a brief rules review, and engaged in the Ludo-playing intervention. Control group participants had their phones throughout the intervention period. Immediately following the intervention period, all participants completed the posttest assessments, which were identical to the baseline measures (N-back and Digit Span tasks). Data were double-entered into an ID-coded database to ensure accuracy prior to statistical analysis.

Data Analysis Plan

Data were analyzed using the IBM SPSS statistics. Before analysis, the data were screened and cleaned by examining the data to determine the presence of missing values, data entry and outliers to guarantee accuracy and completeness. Descriptive statistics were calculated and skewness, kurtosis and the distribution plot were employed for testing the normality assumption. The variables were normally distributed and therefore, parametric tests were deemed to be suitable. The mobile phone detox group and the control group's post-intervention attention and working memory scores were compared using the independent sample t-test to assess the main hypothesis that there is a difference between the groups. Additionally, the pre-test versus post-test variation in the detox group was examined using the paired samples t-test. These statistical tests were chosen as they are applicable to compare the differences of the means of independent groups and the same participants at two time points respectively.

Results**Table 1***Descriptive Statistics of Demographic Variables*

Variable	Mobile Detox Group (n=30)		Control Group (n = 30)	
	n	%	n	%
Gender				
Male	18	60.0	18	60.0
Female	12	40.0	12	40.0
Residence				
Urban	11	36.7	16	53.3
Rural	19	63.3	14	46.7
Departments				
Psychology	12	40.0	13	43.3
Political Science	8	26.7	6	20.0
Computer Science	10	33.3	11	36.7

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of participants across both groups. Both the Ludo Group and Control Group had an equal gender distribution, where 60% were males (n = 18) and 40% were females (n = 12) in each group, indicating successful randomization with respect to gender. Regarding residential background, the Ludo Group had a higher proportion of rural participants (63.3%, n = 19) compared to urban participants (36.7%, n = 11). The Control Group, however, had a slightly higher proportion of urban participants (53.3%, n = 16) than rural participants (46.7%, n = 14). In terms of academic department, participants in both groups were drawn from Psychology, Political Science and computer Science department. In the mobile detox group, 40% (n=12) were from Psychology, 26.7% (n=8) were from Political Science, and 33.3 % (n=10) were from computer science. In control group, 43.3% (n=13) were from Psychology, 20.0% (n=6) were from political science, and 36.7% (n=11) were from Computer Science. Overall, the two groups were largely comparable in their demographic composition.

Table 2*Descriptive Statistics, Reliability, and Normality Tests for Mobile Detox Group(n=30) and Control Group(n=30) on SAS-SV*

	Mobile Detox Group (n=30)				Control Group (n= 30)			
	M	SD	Range	α	M	SD	Range	α
SAS-SV	38.40	6.43	31-52	.79	37.30	5.37	31-56	.79

Note. SAS-SV = Smartphone Addiction Scale – Short Version (Kwon et al., 2013), α = Cronbach Alpha

Table 2 presented the descriptive statistic, internal consistency and normal estimates for Smartphone Addiction Scale-Short Version (SAS-SV) scores in the mobile detox and control group. Mean SAS-SV scores were similar across groups. Mean SAS-SV scores were slightly higher score in the mobile detox group (M= 38.40, SD=6.43, range = 31-52) than the control group M = 37.30, SD = 5.37, range = 31-56), suggesting the comparable baseline level of smartphone addiction. Internal consistency was acceptable for both groups ($\alpha = .79$). The assumption of normality was assessed using the Shapiro - Wilk test, which is recommended for relatively small samples, and the obtained values were close to 1.00 for both mobile detox group (W= .94) and control group (W=.98). The Shapiro-Wilk test was non-significant for both groups (both ps > .05), indicating that SAS-SV score did not significantly deviate from normal distribution. This indicated data normal distribution and supported the assumptions of parametric analysis (George, 2011).

Table 3
Paired-Samples t-Test Results for Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores on N-Back Alphabet and Shapes Tasks in Mobile Detox Group(n=30) and Control Group (n=30)

Variables	Pre-test		Post-test		t(29)	p	95% CI		d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
<u>Alphabet Correct</u>									
Mobile Detox Group	5.47	1.61	6.13	1.46	-1.60	.12	-1.52	.14	-.29
Control Group	4.83	1.97	5.43	1.46	-1.20	.24	-1.62	.33	-.22
<u>Alphabet Incorrect</u>									
Mobile Detox Group	4.53	1.61	3.87	1.46	1.60	.12	-1.84	1.52	.29
Control Group	5.17	1.97	4.57	1.46	1.20	.24	-.42	1.62	.22
<u>Shapes Correct</u>									
Mobile Detox Group	6.83	1.60	7.60	1.28	-1.85	.074	-1.61	.08	-.34
Control Group	4.83	1.97	5.43	1.46	-1.20	.24	-1.62	.42	-.22
<u>Shapes Incorrect</u>									
Mobile Detox Group	3.17	1.60	2.40	1.28	1.85	.074	-.08	1.61	.34
Control Group	5.17	1.97	4.57	1.46	1.20	.240	-.42	1.62	.22

Note. t = t-statistic with df = 29, CI = Confidence Interval, LL = Lower Limit, UL = Upper Limit, d = Cohen's d. Small effect: d = 0.2, Medium effect: d = 0.5, Large effect: d = 0.8 (Cohen, 1988).

Table 3 presents within-group pre- to post-intervention changes on N-Back Alphabet and Shapes tasks for both groups. In the Ludo Group, correct responses on the Alphabet task revealed a non-significant improvement from pre-test (M = 5.47, SD = 1.61) to post-test (M = 6.13, SD = 1.46), $t(29) = -1.60$, $p = .12$, with a small effect size ($d = -.29$). Similarly, Shapes correct responses improved non-significantly (M = 6.83 to M = 7.60), $t(29) = -1.85$, $p = .074$, $d = -.34$. The Control Group showed comparable non-significant improvements across all N-Back measures. These results indicate that the brief intervention did not produce statistically significant within-group changes in letter based or spatial attention,

although effect sizes indicate a small trend toward improvement in the Ludo Group.

Table 4
Paired-Samples t-Test Results for Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores on Digit Span Forward, Backward, and Total in Mobile Detox Group(n=30) and Control Groups(n=30)

Variables	Pre-test		Post-test		t(29)	p	95% CI		d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
<u>Digit Span Forward</u>									
Mobile Detox Group	2.63	.66	3.80	.61	-9.14	.001	-1.44	-.91	-1.67
Control Group	2.70	.70	3.47	.73	-5.43	.001	-1.06	-.47	-.99
<u>Digit Span Backward</u>									
Mobile Detox Group	2.43	.86	3.60	.81	-5.89	.001	-1.58	-.76	-1.08
Control Group	2.40	.86	3.27	.91	-5.07	.001	-1.22	-.51	-.93
<u>Digit Span Total</u>									
Mobile Detox Group	5.07	.86	7.40	1.10	-11.69	.001	-2.74	-1.93	-2.13
Control Group	5.10	1.09	6.73	1.08	-7.03	.001	-2.10	-1.17	-1.28

Note. t = t-statistic with df = 29, CI = Confidence Interval, LL = Lower Limit, UL = Upper Limit, d = Cohen's d. Small effect = 0.2, Medium effect = 0.5, Large effect d = 0.8 (Cohen, 1988). * $p < .05$. ** $p < .001$.

Table 4 presents pre- to post-intervention changes on Digit Span Forward, Backward, and Total scores for both groups. Both groups demonstrated statistically significant improvements across all Digit Span measures. In the Ludo Group, the most notable gain was observed on Digit Span Total, improving from M = 5.07 (SD = .86) at pre-test to M = 7.40 (SD = 1.10) at post-test, $t(29) = -11.69$, $p < .001$, with a very large effect size ($d = -2.13$). Digit Span Forward, $t(29) = -9.14$, $p < .001$, $d = -1.67$, and Digit Span Backward, $t(29) = -5.89$, $p < .001$, $d = -1.08$, also showed large significant improvements. The Control Group similarly showed significant improvements: DS Total, $t(29) = -7.03$, $p < .001$, $d = -1.28$; DS Forward, $t(29) = -5.43$, $p < .001$, $d = -.99$; and

DS Backward, $t(29) = -5.07, p < .001, d = -.93$. The significant improvement in both groups may be partially attributable to practice effects.

Table 5
Independent Samples t-Test for Post-Intervention Group Differences on N-Back Alphabet and Shapes Tasks

Variables	Mobile Detox Group (n=30)		Control Group (n=30)		$t(58)$	p	95% CI		d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
Alphabet Correct	6.13	1.46	5.43	1.46	1.86	.068	-.05	1.45	.48
Alphabet Incorrect	3.87	1.46	4.57	1.46	-1.86	.068	-1.45	.05	-.48
Shapes Correct	7.60	1.28	5.43	1.46	6.13	.001	1.46	2.87	1.58
Shapes Incorrect	2.40	1.28	4.57	1.46	-6.13	.001	-2.87	-1.46	-1.58

Note. CI = Confidence Interval, LL = Lower Limit, UL = Upper Limit, d =Cohen's d . Levene's test of equality of variances was non-significant for all variables, confirming equal variances assumed. *** $p < .001$.

Table 5 presents the post-intervention between-group comparison on N-Back Alphabet and Shapes tasks. No significant group difference was found on Alphabet Correct responses, with the Ludo Group ($M = 6.13, SD = 1.46$) performing slightly higher than the Control Group ($M = 5.43, SD = 1.46$), $t(58) = 1.86, p = .068, d = .48$, representing a medium effect size. For Shapes Correct responses, the Ludo Group ($M = 7.60, SD = 1.28$) significantly outperformed the Control Group ($M = 5.43, SD = 1.46$), $t(58) = 6.13, p < .001, d = 1.58$, indicating a very large effect size. Consistently, the Ludo Group made significantly fewer Shapes Incorrect responses ($M = 2.40$) compared to the Control Group ($M = 4.57$), $t(58) = -6.13, p < .001, d = -1.58$. These findings suggest that the mobile phone detox intervention was particularly effective in improving visuospatial attention as measured by the Shapes N-Back task.

Table 6
Independent Samples t-Test for Post-Intervention Group Differences on Forward, Backward and Overall Digit-Span

Variables	Mobile Detox Group (n=30)		Control Group (n=30)		$t(df)$	p	95% CI		d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
Forward	3.80	.61	3.47	.73	1.85(58)	.070	-.03	.69	.48
Backward	3.60	.81	3.27	.91	1.50(58)	.140	-.11	.77	.39
Digit-Span	7.40	1.10	6.73	1.08	2.37(58)	.021	.10	1.24	.61

Note. t = t -statistic with df = degrees of freedom (58), CI = Confidence Interval, LL = Lower Limit, UL = Upper Limit, d = Cohen's d . Levene's test of equality of variances was non-significant for all variables. * $p < .05$.

Table 6 presents the post-intervention between-group comparison on Digit Span Forward, Backward, and Total scores. The Ludo Group showed higher post-test scores across all Digit Span measures compared to the Control Group; however, differences ranging from non-significant to statistically significant. For Digit Span Forward, the Ludo Group ($M = 3.80, SD = .61$) scored slightly higher than the Control Group ($M = 3.47, SD = .73$), $t(58) = 1.85, p = .070, d = .48$, a medium effect. Digit Span Backward showed a non-significant difference, $t(58) = 1.50, p = .140, d = .39$. For Digit Span Total, the Ludo Group ($M = 7.40, SD = 1.10$) performed significantly better than the Control Group ($M = 6.73, SD = 1.08$), $t(58) = 2.37, p = .021, d = .61$, with a medium-to-large effect size. These results indicate that while both groups improved on Digit Span measures, the Ludo Group demonstrated a statistically significant advantage on total working memory capacity at post-test.

Discussion

The researchers tested the hypothesis that a short, guided mobile phone detox with an offline board game (Ludo) could result in an immediate executive functioning change in the high-smartphone-using undergraduate students. The findings partially supported the

main hypothesis. The mobile detox group performed significantly better than the control group on Shapes N-back task at post-test with an extremely large between-group effect size ($d = 1.58$) (Niu et al., 2022), but there was no significant group difference in the Alphabet N-back or most Digit Span measures. The only exception was that at Digit Span Total, the Ludo group scored much higher than controls ($p = .021$, $d = .61$). These inconclusive findings indicate that the intervention had selective and not general cognitive effects (Canale et al., 2019).

The large effect of the Shapes N-back task is in line with the brain drain hypothesis, which postulates that even the presence of smartphones, even when not in use, demands attentional resources (Ward et al., 2017). It has always been demonstrated that the presence of a smartphone leads to worse performance in activities that require a long-term attention span and working memory, and especially those requiring visuospatial processing (Skowronek et al., 2023; Parry, 2024). This continued attentional cost (Böttger et al., 2023) was probably eliminated by fully eliminating smartphones during the intervention period in the current study. Continuous visuospatial updating and interference suppression seem to be particularly sensitive to such declines in extraneous cognitive load (Oyasar, 2025), as demonstrated by the Shapes N-back task. This is consistent with the Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988, 2011) that suggests that performance on effortful and attention-dependent tasks should first improve in the event of the removal of competing cognitive demands.

Other than smartphone removal, the Ludo intervention in itself might have also played a role in the improvements. Board games involve long-term rule adherence, multi-step planning, response suppression, and real-time state updating of the game, which is all associated with executive control mechanisms (Vita-Barrull et al., 2023; Herrero et al., 2025).

In a Cognitive Load model, this systematic interaction can have facilitated germane cognitive load by focalizing liberated attentional resources into goal-oriented processing, instead of letting them lose into passive dissipation or mind-wandering (Sweller, 1988, 2011). This result is aligned with the fact that the literature on behavioural substitution suggests that passive abstinence does not work as effectively as abstinence combined with an offline activity of interest (Farrukh et al., 2025; Muench and Muench, 2020).

Interpretation of Non-Significant Findings

The lack of important between-group variations in Digit Span Forward, Digit Span Backward and Alphabet N-back accuracy is to be interpreted carefully instead of being dismissed. Both conditions demonstrated a high degree of improvement in all measures of Digit Span (pre-to-post) and the effect sizes were large in both conditions. This trend is a strong indication of the existence of practice effects as a major source of within-group change. In cases where the subjects undergo the same cognitive tasks two times during one session with a short pause between the tasks, performance improvements that are related to familiarity with the tasks are anticipated and already established in the experimental literature (Gajewski et al., 2018; Naveh-Benjamin and Cowan, 2023). The results of the critical finding are not that the two groups were improved, but that the experimental group was not improved significantly more than the control group on these measures, which indicates that the intervention did not result in gains beyond practice alone.

It has task-structural reasons why Digit Span and Alphabet N-back might not be so responsive to such short-term attentional interventions. Digit Span task, especially in the forward form, is mainly an index of the phonological short-term storage capacity as opposed to the active attentional control

(Baddeley, 2000; Woods et al., 2011). Storage based processes are comparatively constant over short durations and are not sensitive to extraneous cognitive load as updating processes or interference suppression processes. Alphabet N-back is more challenging than Digit Span, but presents highly familiar stimuli to the undergraduate student population which might have applied ceiling effects, or lowered sensitivity to small intervention-based effects (Gajewski et al., 2018). This is in line with the data in the literature that verbal working memory tasks are more likely to respond poorly to short-term cognitive manipulations compared to visuospatial tasks, potentially because they demand more reliance on capacity-stable overlearned representations (Draheim et al., 2022).

The aggregate of the non-significant results is not necessarily the evidence of the ineffectiveness of the intervention. Instead, they imply that executive functioning is not a unitary construct and varying parts react variably to short-term environmental manipulations (Draheim et al., 2022; Friedman & Robbins, 2022). One 40-minute session will hardly yield credible results in the entire spectrum of executive processes, especially the ones that entail stable capacity limits. This is consistent with the results of larger studies on mobile internet restriction in general, which have established that two-week interventions generate domain-specific cognitive benefits, but not global execution enhancement (Castelo et al., 2025). The null findings on some of the measures establish realistic limits of what can be accomplished by single-session, short-term detox interventions.

Strengths and Limitations

A number of methodological aspects make the existing findings reliable. The most rigorous method of causal inference that can be used in behavioural studies is a randomized, pretest-posttest, parallel-group design with allocation

concealment

(Campbell and Stanley, 2015), which directly overcomes the selection bias that constrains much of the correlational research on smartphone use and cognition. The addition of the within-group and the between-group analysis ensured a more comprehensive picture: it was possible to determine the practice effects and isolate them out of the intervention-specific gains. The cognitive tasks used in the study, the N-back paradigm and Digit Span, are valid and commonly used measures with well-established sensitivity to changes in executive functioning (Idowu et al., 2024). Their administration was standardized across sessions using PsychoPy software (Mujitaba et al., 2025). The presentation of effect sizes and confidence intervals in addition to p-values provides extra interpretative meaning in comparison to dichotomous significance testing, which is in line with the current psychological methods (Cohen, 2013).

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, practice effect may have influenced the results. As the same cognitive tasks were used at both pretest and posttest but within the same time frame, the large within-group gains on Digit Span measures in both groups are probably due to task familiarity as opposed to the intervention itself. The lack of parallel task versions makes it impossible to separate the practice-related variance from the true effects of the intervention (Gajewski et al., 2018; Naveh-Benjamin & Cowan, 2023).

A second limitation is the short duration of the intervention (one session) as it was limited to a single session. One 40-minute Ludo session is insufficient to determine whether observed cognitive gains would remain stable, increase or generalize with repeated exposure. In addition, no follow-up assessment was conducted, which further restricts conclusion about the long term and real world utility of the intervention (Castelo et al., 2025).

A third limitation concerns with a task sensitivity. For example, the Digit Span Forward task primarily measures phonological short-term storage rather than active executive control and is therefore inherently less sensitive to short-term attentional manipulations (Baddeley, 2000; Draheim et al., 2022).

A fourth limitation is the mismatch of the task and the intervention. Ludo is a visuospatial game and the cognitive demands are a natural overlap with the Shapes N-back task but not with verbal measures such as Digit Span and Alphabet N-back. The marked benefit found on the Shapes task may therefore be reflecting domain-specific transfer, rather than general executive improvement (Friedman & Robbins, 2022; Vita-Barrull et al., 2023).

A fifth limitation relates to related with the characteristics of the sample, which limit the generalizability of the findings. The sample consisted only of undergraduate students who met a threshold for high smartphone use, representing a specific demographic of young, educated individuals already identified as heavy smartphone users. Therefore, the findings cannot be confidently generalized to adolescents, older adults, clinical populations, and average or low smartphone engagement. Sixth limitation concerns sample size and statistical power. Although a sample of 60 participants was adequate for detecting large effects, it may have provided limited power to detect smaller but potentially meaningful differences, particularly across subgroup. (Cohen, 2013).

Implications

The findings have both theoretical and practical implications. Theoretically, selective improvement on the Shapes N-back task offers experimental support for Cognitive Load Theory, which confirms that being able to subtract salient digital distractor frees up cognitive resources for cognitively demanding tasks (Sweller, 1988, 2011). The task-specific

nature of the gains

also adds to the growing consensus that executive functioning is not a unitary construct, and that various components of executive functioning respond differently to the brief environmental manipulations (Friedman & Robbins, 2022).

Practically, the findings suggest that short and structured offline activities can be useful as low-cost and accessible tools for improving attentional readiness in academic settings. Universities and educators might want to consider adding short sessions of playing board games before cognitively challenging tasks as an achievable preparatory strategy (Herrero et al., 2025; Vita-Barrull et al., 2023). In addition, the findings stress the importance of pairing smartphone restriction with meaningful offline engagement, as opposed to just passive abstinence, which has direct implications for the design of future digital detox interventions (Farrukh et al., 2025).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This experiment yields partial experimental evidence in support of the hypothesis that a short, formal mobile phone detox could cause instant executive functioning gains in excessive-smartphone users among undergraduate students. The detox group of Ludo subjects demonstrated a much higher level of visuospatial attention performance than controls in the Shapes N-back task, and the effect size was very large, but in intra-group Digit Span improvement, practice was the most plausible explanation. The results indicate that the structured offline interaction in the process of smartphone withdrawal is better than passive waiting to generate attentional gains, and the gains are task-specific to require constant updating and control of interference instead of constant phonological storage. Future research ought to examine multi-session designs of more extended intervention durations, parallel

versions of tasks to control practice effects, various samples in terms of age and level of smartphone-use, and follow-up to determine the persistence of any so-called cognitive beneficial effects seen. Brief game-based detox sessions have potential clinical and educational uses as low-burden, viable methods of enhancing attentional readiness, but practitioners must have realistic expectations regarding the magnitude of the benefits that a single 40-minute session can provide.

Ethical Approval

This study was conducted in accordance with American Psychological Association ethical guidelines. The study was approved by The Institutional Ethics Committee of GIFT UNIVERSITY Gujranwala Pakistan.

Data Availability

The cognitive task materials used in the present study were the N-back paradigm (Alphabets and Shapes, 3-back condition), which was administered through the use of PsychoPy (version 24.04) and is available upon reasonable request to the corresponding author without undue reservation.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest with the publication of this study. The research was conducted independently and there were no personal, financial or professional relationships that directly influenced the design, execution or reporting of the results.

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